

Online and Offline Marketing Using Aida Framework to Increase Consumer Buying Interest (Case Study: Marissa Holiday)

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ABSTRACT: The tourism sector is one of the sectors that contributes to national GDP, foreign exchange, and employment in Indonesia. One of the reasons for the decline in the achievement of the national tourism sector in 2019 was the Covid-19 pandemic. The implementation of emergency Community Activity Restrictions (PPKM) is increasing weighing the burden on business actors in the travel business segment. The marketing strategy used by Marissa Holiday at this time is to do online and offline marketing. However, in practice the online and offline marketing that is being carried out is still not running effectively. Combined with TOWS analysis, it resulted in the CRM system Marissa Holiday needed to maintain good relationships with existing customers and create opportunities for new customers. Combined online and offline marketing is also highly recommended to create opportunities in new markets such as in educational institutions for travel service providers. This study uses quantitative methods with a sample of 216 respondents. The results of this study showed that offline and online marketing had a partial and significant effect on increasing buying interest in Marissa Holiday.

KEYWORDS: Customer Buying Interest, Online Marketing, Offline Marketing, Marissa Holiday.

INTRODUCTION

Today's tourism has become an important industry in the world, as stated by the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) the tourism industry is a very important aspect in economic development (Nurhadi, 2018). Indonesia itself is a fairly large country that has a lot of natural and cultural beauty that can be developed to become an attractive tourism object for both domestic and foreign tourists. Tourism is the whole of related elements (tourists, tourist destinations, travel, industry, etc.) which are the result of tourist trips to tourist destinations, as long as the trip is not permanent (Sastrayuda and Sedarmayanti, 2018). The tourism industry contributes a fairly high Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and foreign exchange for Indonesia, in addition to tourism being one of the sectors that contributes to the large number of jobs for workers in Indonesia (Kemenparekraf, 2020). Below will be presented data on targets and achievements of the national tourism sector based on data obtained from the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy (Kemenparekraf) in 2020, which are as follows:

Figure I. 1 Data on Targets and Achievements of the Tourism Sector in Indonesia

Source: Kemenparekraf (2020)

Based on figure I.1 above, the achievements of the national tourism sector in several years have shown consistent growth, although there was a significant decline in 2016 and 2019. The tourism sector is one of the sectors that contributes to national Gross Domestic Product (GDP), foreign exchange, and employment in Indonesia. One of the reasons for the decline in the achievement of the national tourism sector in 2019 was the Covid-19 pandemic. The world of tourism since December 2019 has been rocked by the Covid-19 pandemic in Wuhan. The spread of the Covid-19 pandemic is still continuing throughout the world. The World Health Organization (WHO) in 2020 recorded that there were 4,013,728 cases of Covid-19 in 215 countries with a death toll of 278,993 people. The massive spread of Covid-19 has a significant impact on national and international tourism. The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) recorded a decline in international tourist arrivals of 58%-78% in 2020 compared to 2019. This certainly has a major impact on the contribution of the tourism sector to the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP) which has decreased significantly due to the number of tourist visits.(Kemenparekraf, 2020).

Below will be presented a graph of foreign tourist visits and domestic tourists based on data from the 2015-2020 Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy, which are as follows:

Figure I. 2 Number of Foreign and Archipelago (Domestic) Tourist Visits in Indonesia Period 2015-2020
(Source: Kemenparekraf, 2020)

Based on figure I.2 above, it shows that from 2018-2020 number of foreign and archipelago tourist visit in Indonesia tend to experience a significant decline due to the Covid-19 pandemic. This has a very big impact on the national tourism sector, which causes the contribution of the national tourism sector to national GDP or employment to decline significantly. The Covid-19 pandemic itself began to enter Indonesia around

March 2020. Based on information obtained, it is stated that the confirmation of the first Covid-19 case in Indonesia was announced directly by President Joko Widodo accompanied by Health Minister Terawan Agus Putranto at the Presidential Palace, Jakarta, on March 2 2020. The central and regional governments are also racing to test and track cases of Covid-19. On April 9, 2020, 34 or all provinces in Indonesia confirmed a positive case of the corona virus. Until December 2022, information on confirmed Covid-19 cases in Indonesia reached 4,259,857 with 4,833 (0.1%), recovered cases 4,111,045 (96.5%), and 143,979 dead cases (3.4%). Of the 34 provinces in Indonesia, the highest cases of Covid-19 spread are in DKI Jakarta with a total of 864,391 cases (20.3%) and West Java Province with a total of 708,339 (16.6%) cases (www.covid19.go.id).

The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the tourism sector has almost been experienced by various regions in Indonesia. In addition to having an impact on the tourism sector, the Covid-19 pandemic also has an impact on the tourism transportation service business sector. The spread of the corona virus or Covid-19 in Indonesia has an impact on the transportation sector, including bus firms. The most severe impact felt by tourism bus rental companies. The government's appeal to stay at home so that the spread of the corona virus can be reduced, has caused bus orders for tourism needs to be canceled. One of the owners of PO Sumber Alam, Anthony

Steven Hambali, said that many tourism bus business owners were losing money due to the impact of the corona virus. PO Sumber Alam owns a fleet of tourism buses for areas around Central Java. Almost all consumers canceled tourism bus orders which reached 90% (Radityasani, 2020). The impact experienced by the tourism bus transportation service business will continue until 2022. The tourism industry and its supporting businesses are one of the business sectors that have been most severely affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. The implementation of emergency Community Activity Restrictions (PPKM) is increasingly weighing the burden on business actors in the travel business segment. The Secretary General of the Association of Travel Companies (Asita), Bahriyansah Momod, conveyed that the emergency PPKM policy imposed by the government from July 3 to July 2021, did not allow the movement of tourists. This condition adds to the length of travel restrictions that have occurred since last year. As a result, business actors cannot get income. In addition, business actors must extend the period of no activity that results in a 100% decrease in income (Java-Bali) because almost all cities and regencies apply vaccine requirements and PCR evidence (Mulyana, 2021).

The potential for improvement and development of the tourism sector in Indonesia is still quite high. Head of Research Colliers Indonesia Indonesia, Ferry Salanto said that in the remainder of the year 2022 the tourism sector will continue to improve, especially with plans to reopen foreign tourists to Indonesia. This is an opportunity for new investment in the tourism sector. Ferry Salanto said, during the pandemic the tourism industry in Indonesia was only in a "sleep" condition. However, industry stakeholders are still making preparations to face the new normal.

Kotler and Armstrong (2018) state that online marketing is a company's effort to market products and services and build customers relationships through the internet. The need to use the internet as a marketing medium to expand and enhance traditional marketing functions. This definition concentrates on all traditional marketing (Muljono, 2018). Online promotion has an effect on consumer buying interest. Online promotions carried out through the internet, such as websites, as well as promotions through social media. With online promotions, consumers have easy access to information about the products offered (Nur et al, 2020). Online marketing in the current Covid-19 pandemic has become a more reliable choice in influencing consumer purchasing decisions for a product. Although there are still consumers who like the experience of buying products directly (Schulze, 2020).

Online marketing is carried out with an interactive online computer system that connects buyers and sellers using electronic media. Marketing strategies that are carried out properly can convey clear information so that it will affect consumer interest. In other words, it can be concluded that if the marketing strategy carried out is good, consumer buying interest will increase (Fikri and Sahdandi, 2021). If the online promotion that is owned is good, the higher the consumer's buying interest. conversely, the lower the online promotion, the lower the consumer's buying interest (Widodo et al, 2021). In addition to online marketing, offline marketing must also be carried out in order to attract consumer interest. offline marketing has another term, namely direct selling which is translated as a direct selling method where marketers or producers approach potential customers directly with the goods or services offered, for example, property offers by telephone (Cahyono, 2017). Offline promotion has an effect on consumer buying interest. With offline promotions, consumers have easy access to information about the products offered (Nur et al, 2020). Consumers tend to choose offline purchases because they can feel the quality of sales service is better and the risk of buying is lower (Chiang et al, 2018). If the offline promotion you have is good, the higher the consumer's buying interest. conversely, the lower the offline promotion, the lower the consumer's buying interest (Widodo et al, 2021).

Research conducted by Riz'V (2013) reveals that as offline marketing, word of mouth has emerged to be a tool tackle traditional advertisement technique in term of cost, time and spread. Consumers rely on the feedback of existing users and opinions of experts. This reliance tends to be static in the short run. Once a perception has been made about a product it cannot be change overnight and also makes the other means such as email advertisement and chat section. Thus, in order to maintain a positive word of mouth about a particular product should be created and maintained from early in product's lifecycle.

It is impossible to capture most of the audience with the highest purchasing power via the internet, because the target audience does not use the internet at all or uses it occasionally. This is what makes offline marketing at Marissa Holiday still such an effective tool and will be around in the near future. The combination of online and offline marketing may be efficient and can have a synergistic effect, so a marketing strategy should include both. (Bobalo, 2018).

The phenomenon of online (i.e., social media) and offline (i.e., traditional media) marketing communication activities towards consumer buying interest business in the transportation sector is still poorly explored. this raises the question of which part of the offline sales will be genuine and what will be the more effective and efficient crosschannel for Marissa Holiday. When implementing

multi-channel marketing (online and offline), managers must allocate different marketing channels carefully because one marketing channel can reduce the value of another marketing channel.

Due to the growth in the flow of information, it is necessary to find new ways to influence consumers, as internet users advance and the quantity and quality of ad block programs increases every year. Based on the background of the research above, the researchers took a study entitled "ONLINE AND OFFLINE MARKETING USING AIDA FRAMEWORK TO INCREASE CONSUMER BUYING INTEREST (Case Study: Marissa Holiday)".

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Based on the description of the background above and the business problems experienced by Marissa Holiday as a tourism bus service business actor, the research questions to be asked are as follows:

1. What is the influence of online marketing on consumer buying interest on Marissa Holiday?
2. What is the influence of offline marketing affect consumer buying interest on Marissa Holiday?
3. What are online and offline marketing strategies to increase consumer buying interest at Marissa Holiday?

Research Objectives

Based on the research questions above, the objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To find out the influence of online marketing on consumer buying interest at Marissa Holiday.
2. To find out the influence of offline marketing on consumer buying interest at Marissa Holiday.
3. To develop online and offline marketing strategies to increase consumer buying interest at Marissa Holiday.

Business Issues

Since the Covid-19 pandemic entered Indonesia, Marissa Holiday is one of the actors in the tourism bus service business that has experienced a significant impact due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Since the Covid-19 issue in 2019, this condition has affected the world of tourism in several countries, including Indonesia, which also has an impact on the decline in Marissa Holiday's income from 2019 to 2022 at this time. Below will be presented Marissa Holiday's revenue data period 2017-2021 as follows:

Figure I. 3 Marissa Holiday Income Data Period 2017-2021

(Source: Data processed from Marissa Holiday)

Based on figure 1.4 above, it shows that in 2017 Marissa Holiday's income was 1,785,000,000. In 2018 Marissa Holiday's income increased to 2,523,400,000. In 2019 Marissa Holiday's income decreased to 1,943,570,000. In 2020 Marissa Holiday's income decreased to 698,020,000. In 2021, it is projected that Marissa Holiday's income decreased to 468,920,000. The graph above shows that in 2018-2021 Marissa Holiday's income continues to decline. The sharpest and most significant decline occurred in 2020 which reached 64.08%. Below will be presented data on permanent consumers who use Marissa Holiday services as follows:

Figure I. 4 Marissa Holiday Consumer Data for the 2017-2021
(Source: Data processed from Marissa Holiday)

Based on figure 1.5 above, it shows that the number of regular consumers who often use Marissa Holiday tourism bus services tends to decrease from 2018-2021. One of the factors causing the decline in Marissa Holiday's income is the decline in consumer buying interest in tourism bus services due to the Covid-19 pandemic which has an impact on the tourism sector. Therefore, with the policy issued by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy regarding health protocol guidelines for the tourism sector and the creative economy, namely "Indonesia Care" which describes the government's support for Indonesian tourism. Marissa Holiday as a tourism bus service business actor tries to take advantage of the policy guidelines issued by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy by conducting various business process evaluations to increase consumer buying interest in the tourism business. One of the steps taken by Marissa Holiday is to recover the business from covid 19 by evaluate and improve online and offline marketing strategy.

The Emergency Response phase focuses on health, such as initiating social protection programs, encouraging creativity and productivity during WFH, coordinating tourism crises with tourism areas, and preparing for recovery. Next is the Recovery phase, where the gradual opening of tourist attractions in Indonesia is carried out. The preparations are very thorough, starting from the application of cleanliness, healthy, safety, and environmental sustainability (CHSE) protocols at tourist attractions, as well as supporting the optimization of Meeting, Incentive, Convention, and Exhibition (MICE) activities in Indonesia. The last is the Normalization phase, namely the preparation of destinations with the CHSE protocol, increasing market interest, to discounts for tour packages and MICE. One of the programs that have been implemented is the Virtual Travel Fair from August-September 2020 (Kemenparekraf, 2021).

Marketing activities are often interpreted as activities in marketing a product that is traded by the company and shown to consumers. Marketing is a social process by which individuals and groups obtain what they need and want through creating, offering, and freely exchanging products and services of value with others (Kotler and Keller, 2018). Marketing strategy is a marketing logic where companies hope to create value for consumers and can achieve profitable relationships with customers (Kotler and Armstrong, 2018).

The thing that underlies why the implementation of online marketing at Marissa holiday has not been effective is the level of engagement which is still below the average instagram engagement, as shown below:

Figure I. 5 Engagement Rate Marissa Holiday Instagram

Source: Data processed from Marissa Holiday

The marketing strategy used by Marissa Holiday at this time is to do online and offline marketing. However, in practice the online and offline marketing that is being carried out is still not running effectively, especially online marketing through various social media such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram. The ineffectiveness of online marketing is due to the lack of consistency of Marissa Holiday's management in using social media.

LITERATURE STUDY

Marketing activities are often interpreted as activities in marketing a product that is traded by the company and shown to consumers. Marketing is a social process by which individuals and groups obtain what they need and want through creating, offering, and freely exchanging products and services of value with others (Kotler and Keller, 2018). While Promotion is a kind of communication that provides explanations and convinces potential consumers about goods and services with the aim of getting attention, educating, reminding and convincing potential consumers (Alma, 2016).

ONLINE MARKETING

According to Priansa (2017) online marketing (e-marketing) is a marketing strategy, system, and process by utilizing internet-based information and communication technology. Online marketing is a digital marketing strategy using the internet and information technology as a marketing medium. Digital marketing is an application of the internet and is related to digital technology which is related to traditional communication to achieve marketing goals (Chaffey and Chadwick 2016). Online marketing is a must in a company's marketing strategy. Promotional activities look less if they have not used the internet. According to Chaffey and Chadwick (2016) states that online marketing media channels are as follows:

1. Search Engine Marketing (SEM)
2. Online Public Relationship
3. Online Partnerships
4. Interactive Advertising
5. Opt-in Email Marketing
6. Social Media Marketing

Offline Marketing

According to Kotler and Keller (2018) mention that offline marketing is marketing that meets directly with buyers who can communicate in two directions between buyers and sellers. Offline marketing should include print-based concepts. Direct marketing is the use of direct consumer channels to reach and deliver goods and services to customers without the use of marketing intermediaries.

According to Chaffey and Chadwick (2016) states that the forms of offline marketing are as follows:

1. Advertising
2. Personal Selling
3. Sales Promotion
4. Public Relation (PR)
5. Sponsorship
6. Direct Mail
7. Exhibitions
8. Merchandizing
9. Packaging
10. Word Of Mouth

Customer Buying Interest

Buying interest is a measure of customer/consumer desire which is represented by the attitude or behavior of the customer/consumer (Sumarwan, 2015). Schiffman and Kanuk (2015) say that buying interest is a decision as a choice of an action from two or more alternative choices. Meanwhile, Kotler and Keller (2018) state that buying interest is how likely it is for consumers to buy a brand and service or how likely it is for consumers to switch from one brand to another. If the benefits are greater than the sacrifice to get it, the impulse to buy is higher. Based on the above understandings, buying interest is a behavior carried out by consumers which is revealed as a response to an object that will indicate a consumer's desire to make a purchase.

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2018), it is stated that the indicator of buying interest is through the AIDA stimulus model, which is as follows:

1. Attention
2. Interest
3. Desire
4. Action

1. METHODOLOGY

Figure 2. 1 Framework

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

In this phase, the results of the data analysis using SmartPLS that have been carried out by researchers will be presented. The following are the results based on the validity, reliability, r-square and hypothesis testing in this study:

RESULT

Table 4. 1 Outer Loadings

<i>Loadings factor and Cross Loading</i>					
	X1	X2	Y	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Explanation
X1.1	0.714	0.413	0.477	0.585	Valid
X1.2	0.789	0.522	0.475		Valid
X1.3	0.827	0.489	0.509		Valid
X1.4	0.783	0.436	0.412		Valid
X1.5	0.753	0.551	0.498		Valid
X1.6	0.750	0.565	0.579		Valid
X2.1	0.601	0.726	0.520	0.644	Valid
X2.2	0.530	0.815	0.631		Valid
X2.3	0.506	0.857	0.599		Valid
X2.4	0.509	0.859	0.600		Valid
X2.5	0.544	0.802	0.629		Valid
X2.6	0.483	0.814	0.527		Valid
X2.7	0.491	0.776	0.590		Valid

X2.8	0.462	0.818	0.643	0.585	Valid
X2.9	0.522	0.784	0.594		
X2.10	0.532	0.766	0.561		
Y.1	0.428	0.717	0.789		Valid
Y.2	0.442	0.563	0.799		Valid
Y.3	0.488	0.481	0.735		Valid
Y.4	0.633	0.464	0.735	Valid	

(Source: Data processed SEM-PLS)

Based on table III.1, The measurement results have met the requirements of convergent validity where the Online Marketing variable has 6 dimensions consisting of Search Engine Marketing (SEM), Online Public Relationships, Online Partnerships, Interactive Advertising, Opt-in Email Marketing and Social Media Marketing with each loading factor value is greater than 0.7. The biggest influence for the online marketing variable (X1) in this study is Online Partnership dimension with an effect of 0.827. Then for the Offline Marketing variable (X2) has 10 dimensions consisting of Advertising, Personal Selling, Sales Promotion, Public Relation (PR), Sponsorship, Direct Mail, Exhibitions, Merchandizing, Packaging and Word Of Mouth, the dimension with the greatest influence is represented by the Public Relation (PR) dimension with a value of 0.859. Finally, the customer buying interest variable (Y) has 4 dimensions consisting of Attention, Interest, Desire and Action with the biggest influence is represented by the Interest dimension with a value of 0.799.

Table 4. 2 Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Explanation
X 1	0.863	0.865	0.897	Reliable
X 2	0.938	0.940	0.948	Reliable
Y	0.764	0.770	0.849	Reliable

(Source: Data processed SEM-PLS)

Based on the data above, it can be observed that all of the requirements for construct reliability, indicator reliability, and convergent validity were met in this test. Despite the fact that certain loading levels are more than 0.7. There are two loading values around 0.5 and six around 0.6, but Cronbach alpha and construct reliability values more than 0.7, with one Cronbach alpha around the 0.6 limits. Furthermore, one of the AVE values is close 0.5 and the others are greater than 0.5, indicating that the indicators and construct used in this research are likely to provide a consistent result.

The discriminant validity may also be determined by looking at the cross loading of the items. When an indicator's loading on its assigned concept is greater than all of its crossloadings with other constructs, discriminant validity is attained (Hair et al., 2017). Because all of the cross-loading values of the items in the assigned construct are greater than the other cross-loading values, the result shows that all items have discriminant validity.

In table III.3 below reveals the discriminant validity value, it is the extent to which a construct is different from other constructs by empirical standards and in this study evaluated in accordance with Fornell-Larcker Criterion. This technique compares the average root of the AVE variables with other latent variable correlations and the square root of each should be greater than its highest corresponding correlation coefficient. Table III.3 highlights the AVE value square roots in bold and establishes discriminant validity is all met the requirement.

Table 4. 3 Fornell-Larcker Criterion for Measurement Model

	X1	X2	Y
X1	0.770		
X2	0.650	0.803	
Y	0.646	0.737	0.765

Note: The bold values represent the square root of AVE, meanwhile the off diagonals show the correlation between construct R-Squared (R2 or coefficient of determination) is a statistical parameter in a regression model that indicates how much variation in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variable. In other words, r-squared indicates the degree to which the data conform to the regression model (the goodness of fit). R- squared values less than 0.5 are often used to forecast human behavior, since humans are naturally difficult to anticipate. The R squared value of the data in this research is more than 50%, or 0.5, indicating that the data fit the regression model effectively

Table 4. 4 R Square

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Y	0.592	0.588

(Source: Data processed SEM-PLS)

Based on table III.4, it is known that the r square value was 0.592, and this value was in the moderate category. It shows that the Online marketing and Offline Marketing can explain and Consumer Buying Interest by 59.2 percent. At the same time, the remaining 40.8 percent was explained by other variables not included in the study.

Additionally, the collinearity of the structural model has to be examined. Collinearity, according to Hair et al. (2019), may be quantified using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value. The optimum score is close to 3 or less, while a number more than 5 indicates a possibility of collinearity among the predictor constructs. The structural model used in this work is non-collinear, as seen in table 4.5

Table 4. 5 Path Coefficient and Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis Label	Path	Original Sample (O)	t-Statistics	p-Values	Result	VIF	Collinearity Result
H1	X1 -> Y	0.288	3.702	0.000	Supported	1.733	No Collinearity
H2	X2 -> Y	0.520	8.079	0.000	Supported	1.733	No Collinearity

(Source: Data processed SEM-PLS)

Hypothesis 1 (H1) in this study suggests that there is a positive and significant influence between online marketing variables and consumer buying interest variables, this is based on the value of t statistic > t table that was 3.702 > 1.971. The significance level is represented by p-values of 0.000 < 0.05, which fulfilled the p-values < significance level and path coefficient value of 0.288. It shows that online marketing (X1) had a significant effect on consumer buying interest (Y).

Thus, to increase potential customers through online marketing, Marissa Holiday must improve online marketing, the quality of information offered in advertising, social media activation, online collaboration and optimization of all online marketing.

Social media users trust reviews on social media and surprisingly, reviews from other user and friends are almost equally trusted. Thus, Marissa Holiday can use discounts or incentives to get consumers to recommend their products through social media. The

tendency to share positive or negative reviews and opinions seems to be moderate among users. However, marketers need to be aware of the tendency not to share their opinions as dissatisfied customers can easily switch, especially now that consumers have more choices coupled with the ease and convenience of finding similar products/services via the internet.

Marissa Holiday's manager shouldn't use online marketing as a marketing tool just because a competitor's manager is using it. Marissa Holiday managers must use online marketing as a source to obtain in-depth information about preferences and intentions and patterns of consumer behavior to increase consumer buying interest. The role of search engines as a marketing medium or search engine marketing (SEM) is increasingly important for companies. Many companies have used SEM as online marketing. (Nisafani, et al., 2017).

The results of this study contradict the research conducted by Millennium, Suardana, & Negara (2021) at the Startup Bike Rental Banaz Bali which says that online marketing has no effect on consumer buying interest. Research conducted by Mulyatina(2019) on Singapore airlines is also not in line with this research that online marketing is more influential than offline marketing. While the results of this study reveal that offline marketing is more influential than online marketing.

Regardless of the type of offline media used, Marissa Holiday can bridge the gap between the customer experience and offline and online marketing. For example, providing a URL/link in an offline media campaign can help you track the success of your campaign. Marissa holiday can also use different coupons or promo codes for each type of campaign to see which ones are being used the most.

Hypothesis 2 Result

And hypothesis 2 (H2) in this study suggests that there is a positive and significant influence between offline marketing variables and consumer buying interest variables, this is based on the value of t statistic $> t$ table that was $8.079 > 1.971$. The significance level is represented by p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$, which fulfilled the p-values $<$ significance level and path coefficient value of 0.550. It shows that offline marketing (X2) had a significant effect on consumer buying interest (Y).

Research conducted (Widayati, 2018) says that offline marketing is quite important to do and online marketing is needed to complement offline marketing. Research conducted (Chaudhry, et al., 2017) Saying that offline marketing is effective enough to improve purchasing decisions and create brand image, one of them is Marketing Through Print Media. The print advertising process is used to change consumer buying behavior which is directly or indirectly related to Marissa Holiday's value and sales. Today, given the highly competitive business environment, most well-known organizations spend large sums of money on print advertising to increase sales.

Offline consumer buying behavior refers to the buying behavior of the ultimate consumer who prefers to visit traditional stores or contact salesman/use magazines/newspapers/telephonic media for buying any product/service. (Arya, 2015).

In the offline environment, marketing messages can be more easily distinguished from public relations messages, because they often use different communication channels. Another reason for the easily distinguishable nature of marketing communication messages in the offline environment is because various aspects of communication fall under the responsibility of different people in different departments. (Vescovi, 2000).

The decision-making process of online consumers has several similarities and differences between them and offline consumers. Some of the strategies suggested by Marissa Holiday to bridge the online and offline consumer decision-making process. Marissa Holiday needs to encourage customers to search the internet primarily by adding and creating the image of enjoying a risk-free online experience and offline marketing. (Shekhawat & Singhal, 2014).

Proposed Strategy for Marissa Holiday

Based on the table above, it will also explain the strategic recommendations that can be implemented by the company according to this research:

Attention, Interest, Desire, Action factors will affect the effectiveness of online marketing as well as research conducted by Johar (2015) says that the AIDA factor simultaneously affects the effectiveness level of online advertising. Advertising, also known as commercial communication, promotion or marketing, involves mass mediabased persuasive communication aimed at informing about a company's products and services and influencing the target audience.

Ultimately, the ultimate goal of advertising is to generate revenue or at least market share growth. Since the three main domains of advertising are perception, education and persuasion, advertising aims to generate cognitive, emotional and conative responses through a persuasive process that can be interpreted as educational. (Lorente-Páramo, et al., 2021).

Attention refers to “the act or state of applying thought to something”. Although attention has an involuntary component, individuals generally make conscious decisions about which stimuli they prefer selective attention after registering, storing, and processing all perceptual information. Therefore, Marissa Holiday offers consumers an initial stimulus which after processing is considered worthy of attention. Marissa Holiday's purpose of advertising in online marketing is to create brand awareness to target consumers, and social media is used as a landing page to create purchases/closing.

In email marketing, it's common for users to decide whether to pay attention to an email when they check their inbox. While the widespread use of technology and mobile apps allows recipients to make these decisions when they receive a notification on their smartphone, in email marketing campaigns, the process requires action from the consumer opening the email/promotion for actual content consumption to occur. This action is in the "Attention" stage in the AIDA model for effectiveness in both online and offline marketing media such as web banners, where the first interaction with the ad is included in the attention stage. (Goodrich, 2011).

In the online context, there is a strong relationship between interest and interactive media. In general, the website is the most effective medium to attract consumers' interest because of its higher flexibility, even though the website and email have the same markup language, consumers feel a clear difference between the two. Since presenting information that can lead users to the interest stage is critical for effective email marketing, it is not possible to reach this stage unless the recipient opens the email or they are interested in the content. (Hassan, et al., 2015).

From a marketing perspective, desire reflects the aspiration to own the advertised product or service. Desire involves an emotional state in which consumers believe in the truth of the promotional message, aspire to, and even dream about the product. (Wijaya, 2015) The key to increasing the effectiveness of Marissa Holiday is to maximize the quality of posts on social media and the right target audience to meet the specific needs of each market segment depending on their perception of Marissa Holiday.

Desire is a thought that occurs from this desire, related to the motives and motivation of consumers in buying a product or service. At this time arises when consumers or potential customers see an ads online or offline advertisement or promotion that is seen in the promotional media carried out by Marissa Holiday (Kurniawati, et al., 2022).

The first strategic recommendation that companies can take advantage of technology and social media. Using technology and online media, will make it easier for people to access information anywhere and anytime in addition to attracting a wider community. Companies can write about the history, services offered, company contacts, or promotions that Marissa Holiday has. The company can inform the advantages and differences from other competitors in the vehicle industry, especially buses. Such facilities can not only meet the wishes and expectations of consumers but the facilities that are presented are still concerned with safety and environmentally friendly vehicles, this is the application of companies that are aware of the importance of protecting the environment.

Marissa Holiday, a company engaged in the bus transportation industry, has the potential to develop the company considering the large demand for buses and mini buses for vacation purposes, even study tours and many others, this is also strengthened by the proliferation of environmentally friendly tourist destinations that have and tour companies. and travel that is present to enliven the tourism industry will provide many choices for consumers in choosing a destination according to their wishes. With the increasing number of environmentally friendly tourist destinations and tour and travel companies that exist, this will be directly proportional to the increasing demand for buses and mini buses which of course have a direct impact on demand and customer buying interest in using Marissa Holiday services.

With the large number of requests, especially when the holiday season arrives for Marissa Holiday services with 15 active vehicle fleets, there are alternative strategies that can be implemented, including increasing the number of vehicle fleets if possible and providing training and direction to employees in order to make it more efficient and effective. vehicle operational scheduling in order to minimize vehicle waiting time. This is important to do in order to increase company profits.

To solve the problem of the lack of promotion by the company, the company can expand the marketing area by increasing the intensity of Marissa Holiday promotions both online marketing and offline marketing in the hope that consumers can find out the presence of Marissa Holiday.

An advertisement can be said to be an effective advertising when it has reached AIDA. To create effective advertisements Marissa Holiday, enter new unfilled market segments, as school or university for package study tour for company visit. competitive pricing and quality of service is one of key factors, marissa holiday must create intensive relationship with travel agency and enhance publicity with small cost but impactful with innovative and creative flair of massages and increase distribution and increase distribution and try new distribution.

As we know Marissa Holiday has used social media to communicate with consumers. To Maximize Online Marketing, Marissa Holiday can use online partnerships with influencers/reviewers to increase Marissa Holiday's existence and provide new insights about the company in the eyes of consumers. the application of integrated management is highly recommended for maximizing relationships with existing customers and creating promotions for new customers.

For offline marketing Marissa Holiday must work with travel agencies throughout indonesia to add networks and create new opportunities by providing packages to certificate cities. The distribution of flyers in tourist spots is also needed to establish relationship with recreational areas to increase consumer awareness.

Marissa Holiday positions herself as a passenger in shaping her services, with experience as a buyer, it is known that the customer's desire is that the fleet must be good and extraordinary, supported by timeliness Also, good service, and driver's expertise in operating buses. As with the use of goods storage services, it is hoped that they are safe, not damaged or lost. The company does not carry out real promotional activities, because according to its owner, customers already know the quality of Marissa Holiday, which is why most passengers are permanent customers.

To create an "action" from the company's consumers can educate prospective passengers about safety while traveling, so far, the crew and driver of Marissa Holiday bus are directed and trained to always check the bus engine before leaving and driving smoothly. Marissa Holiday management can also help by setting the best bus schedule so that the time for bus maintenance can be estimated.

Regarding high substitution, Marissa Holiday Company must act by maintaining loyal customers considering that most of Marissa's holidays are consumers who have used and experienced Marissa Holiday services. One way is to maximize other integrated management functions, namely by connecting the company's front office and back-office application with customer 'touch points', so it is not impossible for consumers to change their mindset to more quality than price. And with price competition with increasingly crowded competitors, this will not be a problem for the company's loyal customers, given that the cost of maintaining electronic facilities and equipment will be charged additional fees, therefore checking and scheduling regularly will be a solution to reduce costs incurred which is issued management.

Designing standard company systems and procedures, this is something important for the continuity of healthy management, Marissa Holiday requires a system that can integrate components in it in a more orderly and organized way to consider the weaknesses of existing controls. integrated management can also help strengthen company relations with loyal customers. This marketing activity is to increase "Desire" from consumers and potential customers.

Conduct business development by emphasizing the targeted promotion, after creating a customer profile, membership programs are found (because most of them are regular and regular customers, this will facilitate the companies to check the database and identify purchase patterns, where membership will use points. triggers purchases).

Considering that currently Marissa Holiday only has 1 marketing office located in Bekasi, with the aim of being able to reach new consumers by increasing the intensity of promotions and expanding the coverage area such as adding marketing offices on the island of Sumatra. The use of buses so that consumers are not only concentrated on the island of Java. To implement an online and offline marketing plan, not just theory, the plan needs to be executed correctly.

2. CONCLUSIONS

In light of the overall findings of this final research project, three conclusions derived that could be used to address three research questions and objectives as stated below.

1. Online marketing has a significant influence on consumer buying interest at Marissa Holiday. This means that the higher the level of awareness and intensity in the use of online marketing tools will increase customer buying interest, and vice versa if the company is indifferent to the use of online marketing tools, the customer buying interest will be lower. Based on the results of the study indicate that consumer buying interest in buying a product or service is influenced by the way the company maintains its loyal customers by using online marketing tools effectively. This is reinforced by other studies that say consumer desires involve an emotional state where consumers believe in the truth of promotional messages, aspire to, and even dream about products. (Wijaya, 2015).
2. Offline marketing has a significant influence on consumer buying interest at Marissa Holiday. This means that the higher the level of awareness and intensity in the use of offline marketing tools will increase customer buying interest, and vice versa if the company is indifferent to the use of online marketing tools, the customer buying interest will be lower. Based on the results of the study, it shows that consumer buying interest in buying a product or service can also be influenced by the way the company maintains its loyal customers directly to the right consumers because direct marketing can make consumers more appreciated and can directly choose what is needed and not. Needed. While the results of this study reveal that offline marketing is more influential than online marketing. This is reinforced by other studies that say If the offline promotion you have is good, the higher the consumer's buying interest. conversely, the lower the offline promotion, the lower the consumer's buying interest (Widodo et al, 2021).
3. To develop strategy online dan offline marketing, Marissa Holiday can use online partnerships with influencers/reviewers to increase Marissa Holiday's existence and provide new insights about the company in the eyes of consumers. The application of integrated management is highly recommended for maximizing relationships with existing customers and creating promotions for new customers. For offline marketing, Marissa Holiday must cooperate with travel agencies throughout Indonesia to add networks and create new opportunities by providing packages to certain cities. The distribution of flyers in tourist spots is also needed to establish relationships with recreational areas to increase consumer awareness. Marissa Holiday can also combine offline and offline marketing such as creating certain links on offline marketing media such as brochures and flyers or doing ads with third-party service providers Hybrid advertising.

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Cite this Article: Andrey Augusti Mulyana, Isti Raafaldini Mirzanti (2022). Online and Offline Marketing Using Aida Framework to Increase Consumer Buying Interest (Case Study: Marissa Holiday). International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 5(9), 3711-3725